

1 Supplementary Tables and Figures

2 *Table S1: Evidence of Heteroresistance.* Number and frequency of reads supporting each base
 3 call (A_Reads etc), in unexplained amikacin resistant isolates with at least one read supporting
 4 the resistance marker *rrs*:A1401G as a minor variant. The fraction of reads supporting each base
 5 call is also included (A_Freq, etc.). No reads supported an insertion or deletion at this position in
 6 these isolates. No unexplained amikacin resistant isolate had reads supporting *rrs*:G1484T as a
 7 minor variant.

Isolate	Depth	A_Reads	A_Freq	T_Reads	T_Freq	C_Reads	C_Freq	G_Reads	G_Freq
3084-05	148	119	0.804	0	0	0	0	29	0.196
7950-05	82	69	0.841	0	0	0	0	13	0.159
4539-04	239	214	0.895	0	0	1	0.004	24	0.1
TB0892	98	95	0.969	0	0	0	0	3	0.031
TB0733	162	160	0.988	0	0	0	0	2	0.012
TB0362	123	122	0.992	0	0	0	0	1	0.008
TB0368	172	170	0.988	1	0.006	0	0	1	0.006
TB0338	190	188	0.989	0	0	0	0	1	0.005

8
 9 *Figure S1. Cross resistance among Second-line Injectable Drugs (SLIDs).* Venn Diagram
 10 reporting the number of *M. tuberculosis* clinical isolates with overlapping resistance across all
 11 three SLIDs. Only the 476 isolates with phenotypic DST results for all three SLIDs were
 12 included in this figure.

13

14 *Table S2. Association of SLID-R profiles to known resistance markers.* Each row represents one
 15 of the eight possible resistance profiles to the three SLIDs. The columns under *rrs* and *eis*
 16 promoter report the number of isolates carrying each known SLID-R marker with each resistance
 17 profile. As the matrix is sparse, cells with nonzero values are highlighted. The “No Known
 18 Markers” column reports the number of isolates carrying no known SLID-R marker, with each

19 drug resistance profile. Only the 476 isolates with phenotypic DST results for all three SLIDs
 20 were included in these counts. Note that 3 of these isolates carried multiple known markers, all
 21 of them fully SLID cross-resistant.

Resistance Profile R = resistant S = susceptible			Gene					No Known Markers	Total
			<i>rrs</i>		<i>eis</i> promoter				
AMK	KAN	CAP	A1401G	G1484T	G-10A	C-12T	C-14T		
R	R	R	181	3	0	4	1	7	193
R	S	R	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
R	R	S	4	0	1	0	7	3	15
R	S	S	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
S	R	R	0	0	0	5	0	2	7
S	S	R	0	0	0	0	0	5	5
S	R	S	1	0	8	29	2	9	49
S	S	S	1	0	0	2	0	203	206
Total			187	3	9	40	10	230	476

22
 23
 24 *Table S3:* Isolates carrying multiple known SLID-R markers. “Isolate” reports each isolates ID
 25 number. “AMK,” “KAN,” and “CAP” report the isolate’s phenotypic drug susceptibility testing
 26 (DST) results for amikacin, kanamycin, and capreomycin, respectively. “R” indicates resistance,
 27 “S” indicates the isolate is susceptible, and “ND” indicates there was no phenotypic DST available
 28 for the isolate for the drug.

Isolate	AMK	KAN	CAP	Mutations	Lineage
2393-05	R	ND	R	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-14T	East-Asian
TB1236	R	ND	R	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	Euro-American
2-0062	R	R	R	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	Euro-American
2-0006	R	R	R	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	Euro-American
1314-05	R	ND	R	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	East-Asian
6335-05	R	ND	R	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	East-Asian
3176-10	R	R	ND	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	East-Asian
10529-05	R	ND	ND	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	East-Asian
9975-05	R	ND	R	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	East-Asian
TB1237	S	ND	S	<i>rrs</i> :A1401G, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	Euro-American
TB0908	R	ND	R	<i>rrs</i> :G1484T, <i>eis</i> :G-10A	Indo-Oceanic
2-0063	R	R	R	<i>eis</i> :C-12T, <i>eis</i> :C-14T	Euro-American
TB0179	S	ND	S	<i>eis</i> :G-10A, <i>eis</i> :C-12T	East-Asian

29
30
31
32
33
34
35

*Table S4: Association of tlyA genotype with capreomycin resistance. This reports the number of capreomycin resistant and susceptible (light blue) clinical M. tuberculosis isolates with each non wild type genotype in the tlyA gene. *Isolates carrying both the specified tlyA mutation and the known CAP resistance marker rrs:A1401G. **Isolates carrying both the specified tlyA mutation and the known CAP resistance marker rrs:G1484T.*

tlyA Mutation	Resistant Isolates	Susceptible Isolates
-A537	0	1
Asp248Tyr, Asp248Gly	0	1
-CG102, DGLP35-38E, PAVK38-41P	1	0
-G398	2	1
Gly196Glu	1	0
His68Arg	0	1
Leu160Trp	0	1
Lys69Glu	1	0
Ser156Ala	0	1
The134Ile	0	1
Val32Leu	0	2
Val55Val	0	1
*, -A33	8	0
*, -G641	3	0
*, Val55Val	6	0
**, Val55Val	3	0

36

Table S5: Genome position of regions with known resistance markers. This table lists boundaries of genomic regions inspected for known SLID-R markers in M. tuberculosis clinical isolates. These genome positions are in respect to reference genome, H37Rv.

Gene	Genome Position	Orientation
<i>rrs</i>	1471846 to 1473382	+
<i>eis promoter</i>	2715332 to 2715532	-

40 Supplementary Results

41 *Mutations rrs:A1401G and rrs:G1484T Associate with Cross-Resistance*

42 Phenotypic DST results were available for all three SLIDs in 476 isolates, of which 193 isolates
43 were resistant to all three drugs (Figure S1). Known marker *rrs:A1401G* explained 181 of the
44 193 cross-resistant isolates (Table S2). Of the remaining twelve cross-resistant isolates without
45 *rrs:A1401G*, three isolates had known marker *rrs:G1484T* (Table S2). No isolate had both
46 *rrs:A1401G* and *rrs:G1484T* (Table S3). The known marker *rrs:A1401G* did not always confer
47 full cross-resistance. Four isolates with *rrs:A1401G* were AMK-R and KAN-R, yet CAP-S
48 (Table S2).

49 Isolates with full SLID cross-resistance harbored known markers 97.45 (95% CI 43.26-2258.38,
50 p-value < 2.2e-16, Fisher's Exact Test) times more often than isolates without full cross-
51 resistance (Table S2). While no isolate was mono-resistant to AMK, one isolate was
52 simultaneously AMK-R, CAP-R, and KAN-S (Figure S1, Table S2). This abnormal resistance
53 profile may be the result of a mistake in phenotypic DST. The isolate carried a single *rrs* variant,
54 *rrs:C492T*, a mutation present in another eighteen isolates, all susceptible to all three SLIDs
55 (Figure 2). Fifteen isolates were AMK-R, KAN-R and CAP-S, of which four carried
56 *rrs:A1401G*, eight carried markers in the *eis* promoter, and three carried no known markers
57 (Figure S1, Table S2).

58 Supplementary Methods

59 *DNA Extraction and Sequencing*

60 The DNA of all 333 isolates collected for long-read PacBio sequencing, including those of
61 Stockholm and Antwerp, and from NCBI's SRA database were extracted as described in previous
62 studies¹. In brief, isolates were cultured on Lowenstein-Jensen (LJ) media, followed by killing

63 with ethanol and heat. The collected isolates were sequenced with the Pacific Biosciences (PacBio)
64 Single Molecule Real Time (SMRT) long read sequencing platform. The SMRT sequencing
65 protocol was described previously². In brief, PacBio's DNA Template Prep kit without follow-up
66 PCR amplification was used with subsequent DNA shearing. The sheared DNA was end repaired
67 and hairpin adapters were ligated with the use of T4 DNA ligase resulting in a final sample library
68 with insert sizes of 20 kilobases. SMRTbell templates were subjected to standard SMRT
69 sequencing using an engineered phi29 DNA polymerase on the PacBio RS system, as stipulated
70 in PacBio's protocol.

71 *Genome Assembly, Alignment and Variant Calling*

72 To process the original GCDD PacBio long-read data, first raw reads were aligned to the
73 *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv reference strain (Genbank accession number NC_000962.3) utilizing
74 SMRT Analysis's Basic Local Alignment with Successive Refinement (BLASR) with default
75 parameters (v1.3) (<https://github.com/PacificBiosciences/blasr>). Then PBHoover, our custom
76 software³, corrected aligned reads and called variants based on a maximum likelihood criterion.
77 Finally Variant Effect Predictor⁴ (VEP) (v87) determined the consequence of each variant and
78 annotated the VCF formatted files. The 269 clinical isolates, including the 10 isolates from
79 Stockholm and Antwerp, were processed with a new pipeline. Raw reads were *de novo*
80 assembled via the Hierarchical Genome Assembly Process version 2 (HGAP2,
81 RS_HGAP_Assembly.2 protocol; [https://github.com/PacificBiosciences/Bioinformatics-](https://github.com/PacificBiosciences/Bioinformatics-Training/wiki/HGAP-2.0)
82 [Training/wiki/HGAP-2.0](https://github.com/PacificBiosciences/Bioinformatics-Training/wiki/HGAP-2.0)) using default parameters, or via Canu⁵. Circularization was performed
83 with minimus2 ([https://github.com/sanger-pathogens/circlator/wiki/Minimus2-circularization-](https://github.com/sanger-pathogens/circlator/wiki/Minimus2-circularization-pipeline)
84 [pipeline](https://github.com/sanger-pathogens/circlator/wiki/Minimus2-circularization-pipeline)) using default parameters with a previously written protocol or circlator⁶ v1.4.0 with the
85 'all' command and --genes_fa flag set to the H37Rv *dnaA* sequence. Error correction was

86 performed as previously described². Three rounds of consensus polishing were performed using
87 BLASR with default parameters, and Quiver with a maximum coverage of 1000, using the
88 RS_Resequencing protocol from SMRTAnalysis v2.3 ([https://www.pacb.com/wp-](https://www.pacb.com/wp-content/uploads/SMRT-Analysis-Software-Installation-v2-3-0.pdf)
89 [content/uploads/SMRT-Analysis-Software-Installation-v2-3-0.pdf](https://www.pacb.com/wp-content/uploads/SMRT-Analysis-Software-Installation-v2-3-0.pdf)). Failed isolates were
90 excluded from this paper.

91 To call variants, dnadiff v1.3
92 (<https://github.com/marbl/MUMmer3/blob/master/docs/dnadiff.README>) aligned each
93 assembled genome to *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv (NC_000962.3) and call SNPs and small indels
94 with default parameters. A custom Perl script converted the out.snps into a VCF v4.0 file and the
95 Variant Effect Predictor⁴ (v87) determined the consequence of each variant.

96 To process the 851 downloaded Illumina short-read data sequences, first trimmomatic⁷
97 (v0.36) trimmed adapters from raw reads and removed low quality ends. Next bowtie2⁸ (v2.2.4)
98 aligned the reads to the *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv reference sequence (Genbank accession
99 NC_000962.3). SAMtools (v1.3.1) (<http://samtools.sourceforge.net/>) then sorted, filtered out
100 reads with a mapping quality of less than 20, and created an mpileup file for each isolate.
101 VarScan2⁹ (v2.3) called and filtered variants with a minimum quality of 20, a minimum depth of
102 10, the strand filter set to false, and otherwise default parameters. Variant consequence was
103 determined by VEP⁴. Isolates with less than ten reads for VarScan2 to call variants at the sites of
104 resistance mutations listed in Table 1 were excluded from the study.

105

106

107 **References**

108 1. van Helden PD, Victor TC, Warren RM, van Helden EG. VTC. 2001. Isolation of DNA from
109 *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *Methods Mol Med* 54:19–30.

110 2. Elghraoui, A., Modlin, S.J. & Valafar, F. SMRT genome assembly corrects reference errors,
111 resolving the genetic basis of virulence in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. *BMC Genomics* 18, 302
112 (2017).

113 3. Ramirez-Busby, S. M., Elghraoui, A., Kim, Y. B. & Valafar, F. PBHoover and CigarRoller: a
114 method for confident haploid variant calling on legacy Pacific Biosciences data and its
115 application to heterogeneous population analysis. *Bioinforma.* - *Under Rev.* 1–27 (2018).
116 doi:10.1101/360370

117 4. McLaren, W. et al. The Ensembl Variant Effect Predictor. bioRxiv 042374 (2016).
118 doi:10.1101/042374

119 5. Koren, S. *et al.* Canu: scalable and accurate long-read assembly via adaptive k-mer weighting
120 and repeat separation. *Genome Res.* **27**, 722–736 (2017).

121 6. Hunt, M. et al. Circlator : automated circularization of genome assemblies using long
122 sequencing reads. *Genome Biol.* 1–10 (2015). doi:10.1186/s13059-015-0849-0

123 7. Bolger, A. M., Lohse, M. & Usadel, B. Trimmomatic: A flexible trimmer for Illumina sequence
124 data. *Bioinformatics* 30, 2114–2120 (2014).

125 8. Langmead, B. & Salzberg, S. L. Fast gapped-read alignment with Bowtie 2. *Nat. Methods* **9**,
126 357–359 (2012).

127 9. Koboldt, D. C. *et al.* VarScan 2: somatic mutation and copy number alteration discovery in
128 cancer by exome sequencing. *Genome Res.* **22**, 568–576 (2012).